

NODES – Nord Ovest Digitale e Sostenibile

FLAGSHIP PROJECT GRIP

SPOKE N 2 – Title GREEN TECHNOLOGIES AND SUSTAINABLE INDUSTRIES

Deliverable D3.5.1:

New products (Additives, auxiliary and finishing substances, dyes) for a textile supply chain

REPORTING PERIOD	
Period covered:	from M1 to M30
Periodic report date and version:	
Task 3.X Responsible	D 3.5.1 Gianluigi Brogini
RM3 Responsible	Gianluigi Brogini

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Contents:

A. INTRODUCTION

Silk weighting process is carried out on yarns to promote the recovery of weight lost after sericin removal. The treatment involves grafting polymer chains onto the functional groups of the fibroin protein chain.

This method not only achieves the desired gain of weight, but also improves characteristics and performance of the silk. Copolymerization with vinyl monomers is usually carried out by methodologies that require radical activation (redox systems, UV, γ rays, and so on). Methacrylamide (MAA) is one of the most frequently applied monomers in industry. Weighting with MAA involves a simple application achieved with ammonia or potassium persulfate as radical activators. Other activating species usually reported in the literature for radical reactions are not currently applied in industry. For the weighting of silk for ties, methacrylamide is the only technique used by the industry, as no alternative is currently available. The dyeing behaviour of silk may change depending on the weighting treatment.

However, because of the associated risk phrases, particularly H371: "may cause organ damage," MAA is not compatible with the standards of GOTS certification, which is increasingly in demand in the textile industry to ensure sustainability and safety.

The sericin fixation process aims to preserve the natural properties of silk - brightness, softness and strength - making the material more stable and durable over time. Sericin, which makes up about 22 percent of silk's weight, is a water-soluble protein that tends to dissolve during wet processing or after repeated washing. This phenomenon results in a loss of fabric weight, color and quality. To counter this issue, the fixation process involves the use of cross-linking agents to create stable chemical bonds between sericin and fibroin, making the former less soluble or even insoluble. Traditionally, the compound most used industrially is glutaraldehyde.

B. EXPLANATION OF THE WORK CARRIED OUT AND OVERVIEW OF THE PROGRESS

Sericin Fixation

We initially selected possible alternative compounds through literature search and screening through REACH, focusing on molecules that possess reactive groups at the end of the polypeptide chains having a length like that of glutaraldehyde. The compounds

taken into account were poly-carboxylic acids, dialdehydes, diepoxy derivatives, polyacrylates, and poly-aziridines. The suitable chemicals also met criteria for product certifications found in textile. Tests were performed by keeping temperature and time conditions similar to those used on Industrial scale, using yarn as a matrix. Experimental variables were defined by taking scientific articles as references. Activities began in university laboratories identifying the most significant products based on the industrial tests, such as purge and fastness tests. The results obtained in academia were confirmed when applied on pilot scale. Best results were obtained using dicarboxylic acids and diepoxides. However, the former turned out to be suitable only for fabric treatment and not compatible with yarns due to the required conditions, such as the absence of water and high temperatures.

The epoxy substrate was not available on an industrial scale, so an extensive search of the scientific literature and REACH databases was conducted again. This search identified a commercial product that met the chemical and sustainability requirements. After preliminary tests in university laboratories, we moved to company laboratories where parameters such as bath ratio, percentage of product to silk weight, and percentage of catalyst to product were optimized. Once optimal conditions were determined, pilot plant trials were conducted.

C. Results

Silk weighting

The vinyl alternative product has also been GOTS certified and a patent has been filed with UIBM (July 2024), filing number 102024000015850 pending examination.

We are currently conducting trials to make the industrial process and with the partner company bring GOTS-certified “weighted” silk to market.

Sericin Fixation

For textiles we have found a suitable methodology on pilot plants with citric acid to meet all the strength and fastness tests required by the company and customers, the scalability of the reaction on industrial plant is to be evaluated.

For yarns, we found that epoxides are good substituents for glutaraldehyde but do not meet all the strength and robustness tests. Next steps will be tests with other products identified from the scientific literature and optimizing reaction conditions with the identified epoxy products.

Glossary

	Definition
Hub Coordinator (HC)	The Hub Coordinator represents the single point of contact for the implementation of the innovation ecosystem towards the MUR. It carries out the management and coordination activities of the innovation ecosystem, receives the fundings, verifies, and transmits to the MUR the reporting of the activities carried out by the Spoke and their affiliates.
National Recovery and Resilience Plan (NRRP)	This document uses the Italian acronym for the NRRP, which is PNRR (Piano Nazionale della Ripresa e Resilienza)
Research Program Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the overall scientific contents of the NODES project. The NODES will appoint the Research Program Manager. It refers to "Responsabile del Programma di Ricerca" in the MUR's Call of proposal for "Ecosistemi di Innovazione"
NODES' Research and innovation program	NODES' Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spoke, with the aim to promote and support applied research on topics consistent with the Intelligent Specialization Strategy, with the guidelines of the 2021-2027 partnership agreement scheme, with regional operational plans and regional and national research and innovation priorities. Although NODES' Spokes are concentrated on different themes, they will organize their activities and actions within a common framework – NODES' Booster Methodology
Spoke Coordinator	The University in charge of coordinating the Spoke's ecosystem. It refers to "Spoke" in the MUR's Call of proposal for "Ecosistemi di Innovazione"
Spoke Data Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the monitoring and management of data generated at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Data Manager.
Spoke Partner	The entity associated to the Spoke Coordinator. It can be an Innovation Cluster, Competence Center, Research Center related to the Spoke's ecosystem and contributes to achieve objectives and impact under the Spoke' leadership and management. It refers to "soggetti affiliati" in the MUR's Call of proposal for "Ecosistemi di Innovazione".
Spoke Project manager	The person who will be the responsible for the management, coordination and progress of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Project Manager.
Spoke research and innovation program	NODES' Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spokes. The spoke will leverage a consolidated collaboration with leading private and public companies and will focus the applied research activity on technological domains and applications that can favour the integration of SMEs into new value chains.
Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the overall scientific contents of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager.
Spoke Stakeholders Committee (SC)	Consultation structure formed by relevant stakeholders (Government, universities, companies, civil society, third sector, etc.)
Spoke Thematic	General target focus and domain of the Spoke research.
Spoke Topics	Specific areas/lines of development within the Spoke.
Spoke Work Package Leader	At the Spoke level, Work Packages (WPs) will be organized by WP leaders, who will be responsible for performance evaluation and reporting.
Flagship Project	Main research project at the Spoke level with the goal of prototyping, testing, demonstrating the research activities towards higher TRLs.

Table - List of RM3 Project Milestones

Milestone No	Milestone Name	Lead Beneficiary	Means of Verification	Due Date	New Due Date (if delay)	Delivery Date (actual)	Achieved	Comments
M 3.1.1	Availability of database (with digital toxicology analysis) and report of identified chemicals or polymers		Uniform resource locator or digital object identifier	M10 31/10/2023		18/10/2023	YES	File pdf in GRIP folder (30/11/2023)
M 3.1.2	Knowledge of the interests of industrial and logistics companies to design a reverse logistics		Based on the response of interest from industries	M10 31/10/2023	04/10/2024		NO	
M 3.4.1	Identification of products with potential industrial applications arising from enzymatic process		Letter of interest by industries	22 (Ottobre 2024)				
M 3.4.2	Availability of an innovative business model based on the BAT (Best Available Technologies) for the reconfiguration of production processes		Uniform resource locator	24 (December 2024)			YES	File pdf in GRIP folder
M 3.5.1	Planning of related reverse logistics processes based on the use of more environmental friendly materials	3	Based on the response of interest from industries	24				
M 3.5.2	Identification and quantification of the micropollutants in surface water		Letter of interest by industries	26				

A) INTRODUCTION

B) EXPLANATION OF THE WORK CARRIED OUT AND OVERVIEW OF THE PROGRESS